

OPTIMIZATION OF AUTOMOTIVE COMPOSITE BUMPER BEAM WITH OPEN SECTION FOR PRODUCTION AND STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Reduction of fuel consumption, satisfaction of current regulation and in particular the legislation regarding GHG emission and customer safety requirements are the main concerns of today for automotive industries. The effective means to address these issues are mainly based on the possibility of reducing the vehicle mass. In this perspective it is very promising to substitute the traditional steel by lightweight composite material. However, as the mechanical and failure behavior of composite materials are completely different from those characteristic for the traditional metallic material, substitution has to be made by a complete re-design. Beside to take advantage from the specific characteristic of the composite materials, re-design must take in great consideration both production technology and joining feasibility.

Die forming manufacturing technology has been considered for the production technique due to its capability to produce open composite shells with the desired shape and to obtain structurally integrated crash box and bumper beam as a single component. Since open section beams are structurally weaker than similar closed section solutions for the intended loading case, besides cross overall sectional geometry optimization, different set of reinforcing ribs have been used to optimize the structural performance. The result shows that with a proper selection of reinforcing ribs, an open section beam can yield a structural performance comparable with that of the close section one.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reduction of fuel consumption, satisfaction of current regulation and in particular the legislation regarding GHG emission and customer safety requirements are the main concerns of today automotive industries. The first two concerns i.e. fuel consumption and CO₂ emission are directly linked to vehicle weight. It has been proved that the vehicle fuel economy can improve up to 8% by every 10% of vehicle weight reduction. This also means that, for every kilogram of vehicle weight reduction, there is a potential to reduce carbon dioxide emissions by close to 20 kg over the vehicle's operating life [1, 2]. Thus, recently, automotive industries and component producers have been significantly interested to explore the possibility of substitution of traditional metallic components with lightweight advanced composite material ones. Composite materials are generally characterized by high specific strength, both in static and impact loading and high specific stiffness, therefore, the main driving target behind the wide utilization of such materials is weight reduction.

Regarding the third concern i.e. vehicle crashworthiness, composite materials has low strains to fail or a brittle failure behaviour. Under severe dynamic loading conditions like crash accidents, such brittle failure behaviour may result in a catastrophic fracture [3, 4]. Therefore, the direct substitutions of traditional metallic safety components such as bumper subsystem, crash boxes, bonnet etc with composite material may compromise vehicle crashworthiness. Thus, the general objective is to

increase the utilization of advanced lightweight composite materials while developing a new design analysis approach and methodology to ensuring vehicle crashworthiness.

Automobile bumper subsystem is the frontal and rear structure of the vehicle that has the purpose of energy absorption during low velocity impact. Usually, bumper subsystem consists of bumper transverse beam, stays, impact-absorbing materials in the form of structural components and a cover. Among those elements, the bumper beam is the main structural component; it is expected to be deformable so as to absorb the impact energy and reduce the risks of injury for pedestrians and other vulnerable road users, but, at the same time, it should also have sufficient strength to protect the nearby vehicle components. Therefore, during bumper beam design process the challenging task is to obtain the optimal characteristics, since there is a trade-off between strength and deformability.

Recently, the use of composite bumper beams in place of mild steel or aluminium become more common due to the increased number of low volume vehicles and greater emphasis toward weight reduction [5-8]. Particularly, sheet moulding composite (SMC) and glass mat thermoplastic (GMT) have been used in some automobiles. Renault and General Motors used SMC bumper beams in a passenger car instead of steel [9]. In Europe, a special grade polypropylene GMT has been used to develop a 5 kg recyclable bumper beam for the Mercedes S range; Peguform is also using GMT material to make bumper beams for Peugeot [10]. However, as composite material has different mechanical, thermo-chemical and failure behaviours with respect to metals, a direct substitution is not feasible. It needs rethinking the structural design and proper choice of the effective parameters to take the maximum advantage for their utilization.

In composite bumper beam design, apart from material selection, variables such as thickness, bumper beam curvature, rib strength, and cross-section profile are the most important parameters to improve the energy absorption and to sustain the desired deflection of the bumper system. The study for some of those parameters was reported in the literature. Optimizing the cross-section of a bumper beam provide dimensional stability, bending resistance and damping capability [9]. Kim and Won [11] found that the section height is the most effective variable in torsional stiffness of the bumper beam. G. Belingardi et al. [5] demonstrate that beam curvature plays a significant contribution on energy absorption through localization of the failure and then progressively propagation along the beam length. It is also reported that frontal curvature increases the room between fixing points and top extremity beam curvature and increases the stability of the beam and the energy absorption. It enhances the beam stability and extends the required collision displacement. Besides the aesthetic purposes, the curve facilitates additional load impact distribution through the frontal beam and fixing points during the energy damping process. When an impact load is applied to the bumper, the beam initial curvature tends to restore its original shape. So, some designers mounted a bar link between the beam fixing points in order to strengthen the outward motion and the energy absorption tendency [12,13].

In traditional bumper-crash box subsystems, the connections of bumper beam to crash box and crash box to the front longitudinal rails are made by mechanical joints (welding or bolting). Adapting such traditional connection scheme for composite bumper subsystem assembly is not feasible, since composite welding is still limited to thin structures and composite drilling for fastener hole results in both macro and micro damage. Furthermore, the analysis of jointing related problems in composite structures is more difficult due to their anisotropic and heterogeneous properties. The current development in Die forming manufacturing and injection over-moulding technologies makes possible the production of open section composite beam with the desired end profile and of crash box structurally integrated with the beam as a single unit. However an open-channel thin-walled beam component is structurally weak and can readily buckle under lateral transverse loads. With very little lateral support, provided by thin-wall rib-like injection-moulded plastic subcomponent, the buckling resistance (and the stiffness) of the component can be greatly increased.

In the current study, GMT bumper beam has been considered for light weight and better crashworthiness, and geometry and rib optimization has been conducted numerically. The results show that with a proper selection of reinforcing ribs, an open section beam can yield a structural performance comparable with that of the close section one. The idea of integrating bumper transverse beam with crash box, besides manufacturing simplicity, is indeed able to improve both the structural performance and crashworthiness while reducing joining related problems.

2 MATERIAL AND REFERANCE MODEL CONSIDERD

Figure 1 depicts some important dimensions of FIAT500 bumper beam used as reference model. The model is closed with a lower cover of 2 mm thickness and the considered material is a mild steel, with a Young modulus $E= 206$ GPa, density $\rho=7830$ kg/m³, Poisson ratio $\nu=0.3$, and true stress-plastic strain property tabulated in table 1. The beam has an overall dimensions of beam length: ≈ 1200 mm, radius of curvature ≈ 2572 mm crash-box dimensions $\approx 90 \times 90 \times 65$ distance between crash-boxes: ≈ 850 mm.

σ	304.6	344.19	385.51	424.88	450.39	470.28
ϵ_p	0	0.0244	0.0485	0.0951	0.1384	0.1910

Table 1 True stress–plastic strain data for steel.

Figure 1 Reference Model considered : half of FIAT 500 steel bumper beam

Since our main objective is to substitute traditional metallic components with lightweight advanced composite materials, so as to reduce fuel consumption, satisfaction of current regulation and legislation regarding GHG emission and customer safety requirements, a classic glass-mat-reinforced thermoplastics (GMT) is considered for the study. Recently, GMT has gained wide acceptance as the material for structural applications in the automotive industry [9]. It provides a high strength-to-weight ratio, chemical/corrosion resistance, offers greater design flexibility, lower tooling costs, recyclability, greater impact resistance, and elimination of controlled-storage requirements over the thermo-set composites. The main mechanical properties for the considered material is presented on table 2.

Tensile strength (MPa)	110	Compressive Modulus (GPa)	3,258
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	6,4	Shear strength [MPa]	50
Flexural strength (MPa)	165	Shear Modulus [GPa]	2,3
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	5,9	Impact strength [kJ/m ²]	100
Compressive strength (MPa)	65,82	Poisson's ratio	0,28

Table 2 GMT material property considered for the simulation

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION AND MODEL DISCRIBTION

A nonlinear finite element simulation, with a simplified bumper beam model, as displayed in Figure 2, is carried out using the commercial code ABAQUS/Explicit version 6.12-1. The model comprises four parts, two discrete rigid crash boxes, one rigid wall and one deformable transverse beam. The average thickness of the beam is much smaller than the other dimensions of the part (thickness less than 1/10 of the other structural dimension), therefore the best element for meshing such type of structure is the shell element. Besides for typical automotive applications the characteristic element "mesh length" is 5 mm. It was also carried out a preliminary convergence study that suitably confirmed this convention.

The rigid bodies are modeled as discrete rigid surfaces in order to create higher mesh density at critical contact areas. As previously stated, the beam is made of classic glass-mat-reinforced thermoplastics (GMT) i.e. an endless fiber glass mate reinforced PP with randomly oriented glass fibers. The main material mechanical properties are presented on table 2. In order to simulate the vehicle mass, the two rigid crash boxes are coupled at the center and a mass of 1000 kg is rigidly attached on it. The beam moves with an initial velocity of 4 km/h towards the rigid wall.

Figure 2 Mesh and loading

4 REINFORCEMENT RIBS

The recent development on die forming and compression molding composite manufacturing technology allows producing structurally integrated crash box and beam that improve both manufacturing and assembling rate and eliminate connection between bumper beam and crash box. However, it is mainly limited to open section profiles that in bending are generally less performing than the closed section profiles. In this research, the rib-reinforced beam is proposed to increase distortion resistance, rigidity and structural stiffness by adding little material in the open beam section in order to match the required impact performance. Parameters such as rib pattern, thickness, tip and end fillet of the ribs should be designed according to load direction, impact position, material and manufacturing process available. Therefore, five different rib types, as shown on figure 3, were considered and their performance compared for the study.

Figure 3: Proposed Ribs

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Response of the reference model at low velocity impact

The primary function of the bumper system is to protect the vehicle during low speed impact, so as to prevent damage on functionally relevant parts and only minimal or no plastic deformation of any other vehicle component. Therefore, when such metallic bumper beam are subjected to lateral load, the impact energy will be absorbed through elastic flexure and small plastic deformations.

Figure 4 : Results for the reference steel model – 4 km/h impact

Figure 4 shows the impact event characteristic data, such as force/time, force/deflection, deflection/time and energy/time curves for the bumper beam made of mild steel impacted with a speed of 4 km/h. Here it is important to note that, the beam is single out from the bumper sub system i.e. the other component such plastic fascia and foam are not included in the simulation. Besides, the crash box is modeled as rigid part, therefore characteristic data presented in the figure only depicts the energy absorbing behavior of metallic beam. However for actual bumper sub-system (including all the other mentioned components), in case of low speed crash test at 4km/h, the bumper is expected only to bump within elastic limit and without any visible sign of plastic deformation.

5.2 Response of an open and closed beam to lateral loading

For a given thickness and stiffness of the reference material solution, the thickness of the targeted material can be approximately calculated by the expression presented in a previous paper of the authors [14]. Using this roughly approximated thickness material substitution was made i.e. the reference mild still material was substituted with GMT composite material. While maintaining constant material volume, loading and boundary conditions, the impact event characteristic curves and the deformation modes of one open and one closed section GMT beams were computed and are compared in figures 5 and 6. Here once again, the simulation did not include other components but beam only. Figures 5 and 6 show the force- time and displacement time curves and the deformation results for

Figure 5 Comparison of structural response of closed and open section beams

open and closed section beams respectively. Other than beam wall thickness, the overall dimensions of both the open and closed section models are the same as the reference steel model. Both beams failed and therefore need for geometry optimization. However, comparing the two profiles, the open section beam shows unstable and excessive deformation. On the other hand, as previously mentioned, die forming and compression molding composite manufacturing technology that allow producing structurally integrated crash box and beam is limited to open section profiles. As it can be observed on the deformation mode shown in figure 6b, an open section

Figure 6 Deformation mode for closed and open beam

profile component can easily deform and can readily buckle under bending and compressive load. Consequently a proper reinforcement should be added in the beam. With very little lateral support, provided by a thin-wall cross-ribbed injection molded plastic subcomponent, the bending and buckling resistance (and the stiffness) of the component can be greatly increased.

5.3 Beam cross-section optimization

As it is stated on the previous section, except the thickness, the other dimensions of the open GMT beam model are the same as reference model. With the wall thickness selected with the equal bending stiffness criteria, under the impact bending load, the beam deformed excessively. The first option is to change the wall thickness to get an optimized design with similar performance with respect to the reference metallic model. The increment of the cross-section thickness of a bumper beam magnifies its strength, dimensional stability, bending resistance and bumping capability. Figure 7(a) shows an open section beam with end section dimensions. Each section dimensions i.e. width, height and thickness, were optimized separately through controlling

Figure 7 Thickness optimization

the impact characteristic data in order to get the optimum for each dimension. The results of section wall thickness optimization only are reported here while the results of the optimization process of the section width and height are not reported. The reference model, i.e. the bumper beam of mild steel and with dimensions presented in the model description, has a total mass of 6 kg. At 4km/h, it resulted in a peak load of 36kN and a maximum deflection of 26 mm. Therefore, the section optimization was conducted to obtain at least these values then after the beam performance can further improved by introducing ribs. Figures 7 b c and d depict, force vs. time, displacement vs. time and force vs. displacement curves respectively of GMT composite bumper beam with optimized width of 120mm and height of 50 mm and with six different values of the wall thickness. Comparing the six curves, GMT beam with 5.5 mm thickness (indicated by red arrow) resulted in peak load of ≈ 38 kN and maximum deformation of ≈ 25 mm which are almost similar performance with those of the reference material solution. Except for the 4.5 thickness beam, the force vs. displacement curves for the five simulation results indicate that the beams are stiff enough to withstand the applied impact load and the mass will be reduced to around ≈ 50 %.

5.4 Ribs

Having overall cross sectional optimized open beam, the study also proposed some set of rib to further reinforce and increase distortion resistance, rigidity and structural stiffness through adding little material in the open section beam. Parameters such as rib pattern, thickness, tip and end fillet of the ribs should be designed according to load direction, impact position, material, and the manufacturing process available. The five rib types shown on figure 3 were considered and their

performance compared for the study. Each rib type has been subjected to individual optimization using the above mentioned parameters. The results that will be presented here, are only the comparison among the optimized ones.

Figure 8 Behavior of bumper beam reinforced with selected ribs

As briefly stated, the primary function of the bumper system is the protection of the vehicle in a low speed crash (no damage of functionally relevant parts and only minimal or no plastic deformation of any other vehicle component). However, in modern passenger cars, the bumper system plays an important role within the total passive safety concept of the vehicle and has to satisfy all pedestrian protection requirements. Therefore, besides protecting important vehicle parts i.e. strength and stiffness requirements, safety issues have to be addressed.

From the impact event characteristic data, parameters such as peak load, maximum deformation and the amount of energy absorption are important parameters in relation to passive safety. A stiffer beam will have very small deformation and therefore protect the nearby components, however it will result in higher peak load and higher decelerations, which both are dangerous input to the vehicle occupants. On the contrary, if the beam stiffness is not enough to withstand the applied impact load, it may result in smaller peak load and lower deceleration rate but it will not protect expensive vehicle parts and lead higher repair cost.

Figure 9 Deformation mode for beam with optimal rib

Figures 8 a-c show force vs. time, energy vs. time and displacement vs. time curve for the rib types considered and figure 8 d presents compiled summary using data such as maximum force, maximum deformation and few representative data's form strain energy distribution on the impacted beam surface of each rib type. From energy vs. time curve, for all five cases considered, the applied impact energy is absorbed by the beam and it is within elastic limit i.e. without fracture and plastic deformation. However, each reinforcement (ribs) result in different values of force, deformation and strain. From force- time data, for example, rib 5 results in a very high peak load, therefore, with respect to safety, such type of reinforcement will not be advisable. The maximum deformation of all the five considered cases fits with the standard requirements, however comparatively rib 3 results in higher deformation, i.e. weaker beam, whereas rib 5 gives a stiffer structure with higher peak load. In general, comparing the three considered parameters, for the selected loading i.e. low velocity full frontal impact, between the five considered rib types, rib 4 results the better (optimised) solution and can be recommended to reinforce an open section bumper beam.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of a particular constructive solution for an open section automotive composite bumper beam made of GMT has been analyzed. This analysis and the consequent design optimization has been done numerically having in particular evidence the interaction between production technology and structural performance. In order to evaluate the structural performance the more challenging loading condition, i.e. low velocity impact, has been considered. Open section beams are structurally weaker with respect to similar closed section solutions for the intended loading case, therefore, in addition to optimization of the overall cross-section of the open section bumper beam, different set of reinforcing ribs have been used to further reinforce the beam. Keeping constant material volume, each rib pattern was subjected to an optimization process with respect to its dimension (in particular wall thickness), location and number. Finally the best pattern for the intended loading was identified.

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